

Probing the variability of M dwarf stars using Pan-STARRS

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Abstract:

An understanding of M dwarf stars, the most abundant type of star in our Galaxy, are essential to the understanding of our universe. Studying M dwarf flares and variability provides insight into two important fields. First, M dwarf variability can be used to measure the properties of the magnetic fields and chromospheres of the least massive stars. Second, studying flares in these stars serves as a guide for the feasibility of habitability of exoplanets orbiting in the compact habitable zones of low-mass stars. Using data from the medium-deep fields of the Pan-STARRS survey on Mount Haleakala, Hawaii, we have created a large statistical catalog of M0-M9 type stars in the g,r,i,z, and y bands in order to facilitate the study of short time-scale variability of M dwarfs in the time domain. The medium deep survey allows for detailed and sustained observation of the stars, as this area of the sky was imaged about every other night for four years. This paper outlines the method used to identify and classify the M dwarfs from the photometric images obtained of the medium deep fields. The projected statistical sample achieved is about 800,000 M dwarfs of varying class out of a set of about 9,600,000 detected objects in the survey. We will use this catalog to create light curves encompassing about 500 points over 3 years for each M dwarf, facilitating the study of the variability of the star in the time domain.

Introduction:

M-type stars are the most common objects in our galaxy, comprising 70% of all stars (Reid & Gizis 1997, Bochanski et al. 2010), and are some of the closest to our Sun, and yet there are still aspects of their behavior that we do not understand. An M dwarf is classified as a stellar object with effective temperature between 2,300 and 3,800 K. This corresponds to a mass of 0.075 to 0.6 times the mass of the Sun (Reid & Hawley, 2005). This means that while this type of star is very plentiful, there are no M dwarfs visible to the naked eye in the sky, and, when viewed through a telescope, they appear faint and red. Because the stars are so low-mass, they generate energy very slowly through the PP chain, and thus emit very little light. M dwarfs are further split into 10 sub-categories: M0-M9, with M0 being the hottest and M9 the coolest. If the star is less than 0.35 times the mass of the sun, in fact, the interior has a high enough density compared to the temperature that the energy is transported outwards only through convection, without a radiative layer (Reiners and Basri, 2009). These late-type M dwarfs have extremely long lifespans, making them some of the most stable objects in the universe. For example, an M5 star might live for up to 3 trillion years (Adams & Laughlin, 1997).

Chromospheres and M dwarfs:

In models of stellar structure, a chromosphere is the layer that sits just above the photosphere. The density in the chromosphere is low, and while normally invisible, it glows red during solar eclipses. We can detect chromospheres mainly by their emission lines, particularly the H α line at 656.3 nm. It is this emission wavelength that gives the chromosphere its reddish color (Strassmeier et al., 1990).

Of particular interest to stellar models are features of the chromosphere called the chromospheric network. In our Sun, this is essentially a web-like pattern of high-emission (again, seen mostly in H α but also in the ultraviolet in Calcium emission) that outlines the supergranules of the photosphere. The chromospheric network is formed as a result of the interaction between the chromosphere and the convective zone just under it. The convective zones in a star produce supergranules, which, due to the increased motion of the fluid, create the chromospheric network, bundling magnetic field lines into high-density and low-density zones (Freytag et al., 2011). The magnetic field lines, in turn, create disruptions on the surface of the star, in the form of solar flares, prominences, and spicules (Antiochos, DeVore, & Klimchuk, 1999).

The strength of the magnetic field, in Sun-like stars, is thought to be related to the interaction between the convective zone and the next layer in, a radiative zone directly enveloping the core of the star. In this region, energy transport is primarily due to radiation instead of convection, due to the high density of the material. It is the differential rotation of the radiative zone and the convection zone that stretches the magnetic field lines at the tachocline (the transition radius from one level to the other), thus amplifying their effect (Brun, Miesch, & Toomre, 2004).

There is evidence that, in low mass stars such as late-type M dwarfs, chromospheres exist (Mauas et al., 1997). In early-type M dwarf stars, research has revealed that the magnetic field dominates the stellar surface, rather than isolated sunspots in more massive stars (Hawley et al., 2000). This explains the large-scale flares in relation to Sun-like stars. Due to the fundamental difference in stellar structure, however, between these types of stars and later-type M dwarfs, a

different model must be used to describe the observationally apparent flares and H α emission.

The size of a radiative zone is proportionally related to the size, and therefore spectral type, of a star. As a star shrinks in size, the temperature of the core decreases. This causes the radiative zone to decrease in size and the convective zone to increase in size. At about 0.35 times the mass of the sun (roughly M3.5), the radiative zone disappears altogether, and the star becomes fully convective (Reiners and Basri, 2009). If the only method of generating magnetic field activity in a star is through the tachocline, then fully convective stars should not show any major magnetic activity. Yet we know from previous research that this is not the case, and drastic flares have been seen on an individual basis on M dwarfs of later type than M4 (eg. Johns-Krull & Valenti, 1996) – thus we know there must be another process at work to create magnetic fields in fully-convective stars. Studying the differences in the behavior of variability of these two types of stars on a statistical basis may shed light onto the different characteristics of flares on either side of the spectrum, which would aid theoreticians in modeling the different forces at work to create the magnetic field in the interior of each type of star (e.g. France et al., 2013).

Exoplanets and M dwarfs:

Exoplanet hunting, with the aid of numerous specialized telescopes built for the task, has seen a huge upswing in the recent past. Especially with the advent of the Kepler mission, known exoplanets – or planets orbiting a star other than our Sun – have increased from a few to a few thousand (Batalha et al., 2013). Interest in exoplanet hunting has only increased as planets with characteristics fortuitous to the development of life are discovered. In addition to being near

Earth-sized, in order for a planet to be habitable, it must reside within what is known as the “habitable zone” – that is, the distance from the star at which liquid water can exist on the surface.

There are two major ways of detecting planets: one, by measuring the flux coming from the star as the planet transits in front of the star, blocking some of its light. The other method is the “wobble method,” where the radial velocity of the star will change as it and the planet orbit around their common center of mass. In the former method, the probability of us being able to observe a transit of the planet increases as the planet gets closer to its star (because the 2D projection of the planet is more likely to fall on the star) (Boruki & Summers, 1984, Barnes, 2007) .

M dwarfs present the best of both worlds, as they are very abundant in the galaxy (and thus harbor a large percentage of the Galaxy's exoplanets) and happen to be of a size/luminosity to make detection of an exoplanet in the habitable zone much more probable than an exoplanet around, say, a G-type star. Assuming a circular orbit, the equation for the probability of a transit

is: $p = \frac{R_{star}}{d}$, where R is the radius of the star, and d is the distance from the star to the exoplanet (Boruki & Summers, 1984). While an M dwarf has a smaller radius than a G star, it has a much smaller effective temperature, bringing in the habitable zone to a much smaller d. Thus, for example, a planet receiving the same flux as the Earth, but orbiting around an M5 star, would be at a distance of only 0.074 AU. The probability of this transit would be 0.016, as opposed to 0.005 of the Earth (Nutzman & Charbonneau, 2008). In addition, their small size means that an orbiting exoplanet would block a greater percentage of the star's flux, creating larger

characteristic dips in flux (Kasting et al., 1993) (the dip in flux is proportional to $\frac{R_{planet}}{R_{star}}$).

Finally, the orbital period which is proportional to $\frac{d^{3/2}}{M}$ (where M is the mass of the star) is much less for a planet around an M dwarf, providing more frequent observable transits. The Mearth project seeks to do just this: detect habitable exoplanets around nearby M dwarfs using the transit detection method (Irwin, Charbonneau, et al. 2009).

Yet variability in M dwarfs presents a fundamental challenge to life developing on such a planet, as well as the detection of such a planet. M dwarfs are known to have some of the most extreme variability of all main-sequence stars flaring up in a time span of a few days (Scalo et al., 2007). Short-term variability presents a challenge to detecting dips in flux corresponding to an exoplanet transit. The transit, in fact, could be masked by a flare, especially in the blue optical and in the UV parts of the spectrum (Knutson et al., 2011). Not only that, but these flares eject large amounts of radiation, which could potentially penetrate the atmosphere of an orbiting planet. The atmosphere of such a planet would constantly be adjusting to new equilibria, with drastic changes in color (Scalo et al., 2007). On the other hand, if the star were completely static, UV rays needed to stimulate the combination of organic material might not be able to penetrate the atmosphere, and life might never form in the first place. This makes accurate statistical analysis of flares in M dwarfs essential for determining the feasibility of life on a planet orbiting each of the M dwarf sub-categories. Thus, accurate studies on the time-dependent variability of M dwarfs is essential for a variety of astronomical studies.

Previous Work:

Previous attempts to answer this question of M dwarf variability has been limited by the availability of a survey which could image not only a large number of faint stars, but which could continually image these same objects with sufficient frequency that short time-span flares on the order of a few days could be accurately detected. Studies have been done to measure the variability of M dwarfs in many different wavelengths, although always on a smaller scale than this project attempts. Kruse et al, in 2010, analyzed the short-timescale H α variability of 50,000 M dwarfs in Sloan Digital Sky Survey. They used 15 minute spectroscopic exposures, finding that 16% of the objects had emission in one exposure, and of that, 45% had sustained emission in all exposures (Kruse et al., 2010). There were only 3-30 exposures per object, however. Even still, this data begs to be corroborated with photometric observation.

Most notably to that end, in 2011, John Bochanski, Suzanne Hawley, and Andrew West did a study of variability of Balmer series emission on some 70,000 M dwarfs in Sloan Digital Sky Survey. This study was limited by the number of sources, as well as the relatively infrequent observation times – thus while they could observe variability on a large scale, they missed many of the flares that would require nightly observation (Bochanski, Hawley, & West, 2011).

In the optical regime, Kowalski et al., 2009 conducted a study on 50,000 M dwarfs from SDSS strip 82 in the optical: u and g bands. They detected 271 flares, ranging in type from M0 to M6. While this attempt contributed considerable knowledge to the flaring behavior of early-type M dwarfs, it was limited in a few ways: 1, that it only observed objects to M6, limiting the amount of information gleaned about cool M dwarfs, where the convection-based dynamo would be observable, and 2, that it only took about 70 observations over the course of 6 years, severely limiting the ability to detect short-time scale flares.

On the other end of the spectrum, a paper published in 2011 by H. L. Woters, G. E. Bromage, and D. A. H. Buckley reported on three M dwarf flares studied in great depth in the UV spectrum by SALT. While time resolution on these sources was extremely high (.15 seconds), only three sources were included in the study, and thus no generalizations could be drawn about M-stars as a class (Woters et al., 2011). In addition, Berger et al., 2008, did a detailed analysis of two single flare sources, M8.5 and M8. These observations were done in a variety of wavelengths, including radio, X-ray, UV, and optical. The observations were done for a total of 9 hours, and revealed H α variability on timescales of 1.5-2 hours. This confirmed the magnetic activity of late-type, fully-convective M dwarfs, but could not say anything about the general, statistical behavior of that activity.

Serendipitously, just a few weeks ago, a paper was published by Gezari et al., classifying over a thousand variable stars (of which 53 are M dwarf flares) in the UV band using GALEX. The sources were purposely coordinated with the Medium-Deep field of Pan-STARRS, which bodes well for future multi-wavelength study of a select number of M dwarfs found in the Pan-STARRS survey. The time-span on the GALEX survey is remarkably similar to Pan-STARRS, with a cadence of 2 days and a total observing frame of around 3 years (Gezari et al., 2013).

The Pan-STARRS study of M dwarfs provides the missing link between the various studies of flare stars, collecting a large number of sources with a very short cadence time. The time is ripe for flare studies.

Pan-STARRS:

The Pan-STARRS project came out of the need for a “large synoptic survey telescope,” as articulated in the 2000 Decadal Review. The original science goals of the telescope were many,

ranging from near Earth object detection to measurements of large scale structure of the universe. The wide field of view and ability to image faint Milky Way objects in the optical, however, makes the telescope perfect for imaging dwarf stars such as M dwarfs in our local galaxy.

The telescope is located at the summit of Haleakalā on Maui, Hawaii. It is a 1.8 meter mirror with a 7 square degree field of view in the sky. The optics work on a Cassegrain system with a refractive corrector. The attached CCD contains 1.4 billion pixels, broken up into an 8x8 grid of CCDs (excluding the corners). Each of these 50 CCDs is further split into 10 sky-cells each, which are split into quarters. These CCDs are sensitive from a wavelength of about 400nm to about 1000nm. The optical filters of the telescope are: g-band at 402-552 nm, r-band at 552-691 nm, i-band at 691-818 nm, z-band at 818-922 nm, and y-band at 948-1060nm (Kaiser et al., 2010). Our data comes from exposures taken almost nightly for three years. The specifications of Pan-STARRS currently make it capable of repeatedly imaging objects of up to around 23.5 magnitudes (Kaiser et al., 2010).

In particular, the Medium-Deep Fields provide the level of frequency of observation that we need in order to accurately measure the short-term variability of M dwarfs. The Medium-Deep Survey is a collection of 10 patches on the sky, dispersed randomly, which are observed almost every night, with an exposure time ranging from 113 seconds to 240 seconds (depending on the color band). The locations of the Medium-Deep Fields, from which we created our catalog, are listed below in Table 1 (Tonry et al., 2012). In Table 2 is listed the timeline of the observations in the different filters, to show the frequency of the observations (Tonry et al., 2012).

Data Retrieval:

We used the program Source Extractor to detect sources on the sky cells of the Medium-Deep fields. Source Extractor essentially reduces our data for us. It calculates the FWHM of each image and performs aperture photometry (as well as a few other kinds of photometry), using the FWHM to find the calibrated magnitude for each object detected. The advantage of Source Extractor, rather than the standard PanSTARRS source finder, is that we can understand and tweak all the parameters in the program – how the program performs astrometry, what flags it assigns to potentially corrupted data, and why. In addition, Source Extractor allows for the possibility of detecting sources on one image and doing photometry on another, allowing us to easily track our sources through different observations.

To create a catalog of M dwarfs, we used the stacked images Pan-STARRS provides for that purpose. The stacked images overlay multiple individual exposures (image coadd). Thus, they go deeper than the exposures themselves. Because of this, we will be able to detect faint objects which might not be visible in any one exposure, and track the position of that object. Next, we ran Source Extractor on one of these stacked images (one quarter of one sky cell of one CCD of one field of view). The method of cutting unwanted objects will be developed on only this file – for the rest of the paper, we will be examining this one image, and then at the end we will extrapolate these results to get an estimate for the projected full catalog (which will be completed, due to computing time restraints, after the semester is over). Once we have run Sextractor, we rid the source sample of all corrupted sources: sources which, for one reason or another, cannot give us a reliable magnitude reading. Source Extractor places flags on objects of varying number based on the error in photometry in extracting that source. The possible flags

and their corresponding numbers are listed in the manual (Holwerda, p. 71-72). Since our sample of objects is quite large (and we are not worried about having too small a sample), our first cut was to reject from the sample all objects that had any flags whatsoever.

The three types of photometry that Source Extractor is capable of performing are: isophotal, a type Source extractor calls “automatic” (set in the system), and aperture. Isophotal photometry integrates flux by creating contour lines around areas of fixed brightness. Aperture photometry, on the other hand, creates circles of fixed width based on the full-width half-max of the image, and sums the flux within these circles. “Automatic” photometry, the default feature of Source Extractor, works similarly to aperture photometry, except that it uses ellipses instead of circles. Figure 1 illustrates the techniques of photometry (taken from the Source Extractor manual).

We are looking to find two pieces of information from photometry: the color of our sources (so that we can classify the sources into star types) and the differences in magnitude in each color band over time. Thus, our primary restrictions on photometry are that it must be 1) consistent from image to image and 2) be free of contamination from background light or blending with a nearby source. Since our objects are primarily point sources, we can exclude isophotal photometry, since it is mostly used for diffuse objects like galaxies. In addition, we can exclude “automatic” photometry, because the eccentricity of the ellipse is too linked to the parameters of that particular image – making it inconsistent over different color-band images. Thus, we decided to use aperture photometry.

Our next task was to determine where to distinguish between background and flux. Source Extractor allows the use of multiples of the FWHM. We decided to compare 2 times the

FWHM and 5 times the FWHM, both of which capture enough flux to accurately classify the object but cut off soon enough to prevent blending. Whichever matched best with the “automatic” photometry (which would be best on an image to image basis) would provide the most accurate measurement of magnitudes within an image, while still being consistent with other color-bands. Figure 2 shows the correlation between automatic photometry and 2FWHM on one image ($\frac{1}{4}$ of one sky cell) while Figure 3 shows the correlation between automatic and 5FWHM, using only sources with zero flags.

From these graphs, we deduced that using 5 times the FWHM would provide the most consistent estimates for magnitude, being consistent both with the automatic photometry in each image and across the color bands. This plot also gave us a hint as to where our cutoff point might be for detections. The width of the magnitude correlation stays within about 0.2 magnitudes through aperture magnitude 24, an acceptable amount for the color scale we are working with. This tells us that we can be fairly certain of the magnitude calculations done by Source Extractor up to that point. We did not use this as the definitive measure for cut-off magnitude, but rather used it as a check for our other method of determining the cut-off point. Thus we were able to extract the x pixel coordinates, y pixel coordinates, right ascension, declination, magnitude in 5 color bands, and associated errors on that magnitude for each source detected in the field.

M Dwarf Extraction:

Having extracted information about the sources using Source Extractor, we were now ready to interpret the data by picking out the stars based on their color-color characteristics, and

ultimately extract from that pool the M dwarfs.

Our first method of star extraction was to cut sources with flags. Figures 4 and 5 show our total sample of zero-flag sources on two different color-color axes – r-i versus i-z and g-r versus r-i. In Figure 4, the overdensity of points along a line indicates where the stellar locus lies, or the r-i and i-z behavior of stars along the main sequence. Objects that do not fall on this line are likely non-stars or stars with unreliable photometry, and thus need to be cut from the plot.

In addition, it is important to find a way to classify objects that are not detected in r-band. These faint objects often have i-z magnitudes consistent with later-type M dwarfs (which are by nature fainter due to their lower luminosity and cooler temperature), and thus are essential in getting a robust sample of M6 and beyond. In order to set a lower limit on the r-band magnitude of these points, we averaged together the magnitudes of those points with error around 3 sigma (3-3.5 sigma) and took this average value to be the minimum magnitude for r-band non-detections. Thus, for those with detections, we can be 99.7% certain of having the correct magnitude. We did the same process for g-band non-detections: averaged together the magnitudes of points with error 3-3.5 sigma. Our results, for this specific field, were r-band limit of 24.83 magnitudes, and g-band limit of 24.85. These, of course will vary for each exposure based on the observing conditions that night, and of course will all be lower than for these deeper catalog-oriented overlays. A note was set for all these sources in the catalog, indicating their inferior status in terms of certainty of classification.

Extendedness:

Early on, we attempted to use the extendedness value from Source Extractor. Extendedness runs from 0 to 1, with 1 being the most star-like and 0 the most diffuse (galaxy-like). Source Extractor finds extendedness on the basis of a Neural Network Output. The characterization depends on a variety of inputs, including pixel scale, seeing FWHM, size of a background mesh, etc (Holwerda). To get a good sense of the star population vs. galaxy population in our field, we plotted the number of stars detected using different cutoff values for extendedness; only sources with extendedness values above that cutoff would be counted as stars, while those below were thrown out of the sample as galaxies or other objects. Figure 6 shows the result of that study.

This plot shows that Extendedness is not a good indicator as to the status of a source as a star or galaxy. This is most likely due to the fact that the sources are so faint. The manual warns that at fainter magnitudes, the effectiveness of “Extendedness” breaks down. At some of the faintnesses that we are dealing with (20 and up), it would be near-impossible to characterize the source as diffuse or point-like, as there simply is not enough flux from the star to distinguish a definite shape. The objects that had very low extendedness parameters are likely bright galaxies in the sample. We set the extendedness cutoff to be .3, as to cut these bright galaxies out. For faint objects, a different method was necessary to separate the stars from the total sample.

Stellar Locus Modeling:

A study was done by Covey et al. in 2007, plotting the colors of around 600,000 stars in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey catalog in order to get an accurate description of the stellar locus of main-sequence stars, comparing different colors. In particular, we were able to make use of the

i-z v r-i stellar locus shape as well as the r-i v g-r shape to cut down our sample, as well as to determine the error on our classification of each source as a non-star or as a star. Figure 7 is taken from Figure 2 in that paper, showing the trends for the 600,000 SDSS stars.

This figure provides a good roadmap for quantifying the degree of certainty about a stellar classification as opposed to a non-stellar classification. In the i-z v r-i plot, the stellar locus follows a roughly linear pattern, making it easy to model the stellar locus and its sigma uncertainty. In the r-i v g-r plot, however, the points with r-i larger than about 0.5 (which is the vast majority of the M dwarf classifications) follow a constant pattern, centered around g-r of about 1.3. Rather than try to model the stars based on this line (a difficult task due to the large number of non-detections in r-band and the larger number of detections in the g-band) we can use this information to place a check on sources with detections in all five color bands.

Using the table of values (Covey et al, Table 1) provided along with the images (Table 3) we fit three lines to the i-z v r-i graph, one representing the color locus, and the other two representing the one sigma values on either side. The table in Covey uses as a basis the g-i color of the star, but we can use the r-i column instead, since the correlation is one-to-one. We can use this fact, however, to check, for sources with g-band detections, whether the g-i value matches the corresponding r-i and i-z values (since the table includes correlations between all these values). While the Covey paper fits a 5th order polynomial to the table itself, we decided to make our own using the IDL procedure Linfit, because we are only interested in the range of g-i that corresponds to M dwarfs – a small subset of the table as a whole (which, in the i-z versus r-i graph, is roughly linear in our region of interest). Thus we wanted the fit to match well only in this region, and did not worry about whether it diverged outside this range. From here we could

calculate the total standard deviation of each source from the stellar locus, taking into account both the error bars on the source magnitudes and the error on the stellar locus.

Sloan Digital Sky Survey v Pan-STARRS z-band calibration:

One important fact cannot be overlooked. The stellar locus, as well as the M dwarf classifications, are defined in terms of SDSS magnitudes, due to the large amount of study done on that survey. Our sources, however, are in the Pan-STARRS survey and thus are subject to the specifications of the PS1 color bands. For the most part, these match the SDSS bands (there are slight differences, but for r,i, and g bands, these provide a negligible difference). SDSS and Pan-STARRS, however, calculate the z-band flux differently, due to the different natures of the filters. In SDSS, the z-band filter is an open filter: essentially, anything above 8000 angstroms will be caught in the z-band. The upper limit is therefore due to the CCD response, and not due to any concrete cutoff point. However, in Pan-STARRS there is a filter above the z-band, the y-band filter. Thus, the z-band in PS1 has a low cutoff and a high cutoff, just like any other color band, and is not tapered due to CCD response. Thus the z-band magnitudes in Pan-STARRS are slightly lower, on average, than the SDSS z-band magnitudes.

In order remedy this problem, we converted the Pan-STARRS z-band magnitudes to SDSS z-band magnitudes for stellar classification and error (keeping track of the original z-band magnitudes for after the catalog is created). We used a third order polynomial with parameters [0.02214, 0.17233, -0.14187, 0.09631] in order to find the difference between the SDSS z-band magnitude and the PS1 z-band magnitude, as a function of the PS1 i-z magnitude (Polynomial fit thanks to Douglas Finkbeiner). This gave us the equation:

$$z_{sdss} - z_{psl} = 0.02214 + 0.17233(i - z_{psl}) - 0.14187(i - z_{psl})^2 + 0.09631(i - z_{psl})^3$$
 Figure 8 shows the plot of the changes to the z-band magnitudes. The polynomial fit guarantees error less than 0.01 magnitudes for $0.05 < i - z < 1.5$. For sources with $i - z$ less than 0.05, where the polynomial fit diverges, we kept the same z-band magnitude. These sources are so blue anyway that the correction would be extremely minor.

Once our z-band magnitudes have been converted, we are ready to calculate the total error on our classifications. We used the schema, pictured in Figure 9. Distance a represents the total error on the point itself, using the errors in the r-i estimate and the i-z estimate. Distance b represents the shortest distance from the point itself to the stellar locus. Distance c represents the one sigma error on the stellar locus itself. By taking the value $b/(a+c)$, we have an accurate estimate to the standard deviation of the point from the stellar locus, and thus a standard deviation of the error in classifying that point as a star.

Using this method, we can isolate all the sources that fall within two sigma of the stellar locus, and classify these objects as stars. Performing the cuts described above and accepting all points within two sigma gives us the following plot of stars, shown in Figure 10.

Thus we have classified objects as stars based on distance to stellar locus as well as g-r limit and g-i limit (for those sources with g-band detections). We can be fairly certain that our final sample of sources, after all these cuts, is pure. This is good, because our study relies more on purity than completeness.

We created also a separate pool of sources, those with r-band magnitude limits due to non-detections in r-bands. Since we do not have enough color-band detections of these objects to classify them as stars in the usual way, we must simply assume they are stars, and that their

types can be gleaned from their $i-z$ magnitudes alone. Understandably, we will be less certain about the status of these objects as stars than sources with more detections. However, we can perform a cut based on $i-z$ to ensure that this sample is as certain as possible, under the circumstances. Referring back to Figure 4, at a certain limit, around $i-z > 1.2$, we do not see any sources with well-defined r -band magnitudes. We can conclude that the contamination in this region of non-starlike objects is low, and thus we can deduce that the majority of objects found in this region are stars, pushed leftwards off the stellar locus by the limitations in r -band detection of the telescope, and will keep all of these $i-z > 1.2$ objects as a separate, limit-based M dwarf sample. Later in the study, when we begin to study the time-dependent behavior of the sources in the sample (mostly M6-M9s), we can get a clue as to the purity of this sample by how well the behavior of the sample as a whole matches the behavior of M6-M9 stars with definite r -band detections.

The last step that remains is to split these stars into M dwarf classifications, and after this our catalog will be complete, with robust information on each source in multiple color bands.

Classification of M dwarfs:

Classification of M dwarfs within our star sample relied on the usage of a study by West et al. in 2011, which used SDSS spectroscopic data to find color-color ranges for each M dwarf type. The numbers were based off a catalog of 70,841 M dwarfs (about a tenth of what we expect to see). West et al visually inspected 116,161 candidates in the survey, and using the Hammer spectral typing facility (Covey et al., 2007), assigned spectral types to these objects. Of the original candidates, 70,841 were classified as M dwarfs with signal-to-noise large enough for

a classification with high confidence (West et al., 2011). These objects were used to model the color-color characteristics of the different spectral classes of M dwarfs. The catalog was cross-matched with the Two Micron All-Sky Survey for added checks on accuracy. Table 3 (taken from Table 2 in West et al.) shows the results of that study.

Of course, these ranges are defined by the z-band magnitudes in SDSS, so in order to classify our sources, we must use the shifted z-band magnitudes of each source, as we did for finding the distance to the stellar locus. Figure 11 shows the final results of our cuts.

In order to generate the spectral type of each star, we found the nearest M dwarf box to the point. In cases where a star is closest to two overlapping boxes (ex. M6 and M7), the star is always classified in the lower category, for convenience. By categorizing the sources by spectral class, we can use the luminosity of that spectral class to estimate the distance to each source, in addition.

Results:

Our research was successful in that we were able to create a catalog of M dwarfs of varying spectral types, creating cuts to make as pure of a sample as possible. In our one-quarter sky-cell, we were able to extract 346 M dwarfs within two sigma of the stellar locus, out of a sample of 4176 objects total. Our sample was one catalog file of 2173 total files (roughly $4 \times 10 \times 60$ M dwarfs total in the Medium-Deep Field (4 to get one full sky-cell, 10 for the number of sky-cells per CCD, and 60 for the number of CCDs in the array). For these M dwarfs, we

recorded the x position (on the sky-cell), y position, right ascension, declination, g-band magnitude and error, r-band magnitude and error, i-band magnitude and error, z-band magnitude and error, and y-band magnitude and error. In addition, we record for each M dwarf a series of values that allow us to assess the certainty of that object as a star: whether g-r magnitude matches, whether the g-i magnitude matches, and the standard deviation away from the stellar locus. Additionally, we have a projected sample of 24,000 sources that fit the i-z color for M dwarfs, but which don't have an r-band detection, only an r-band limit.

Future Work:

This work constitutes the first half of a larger project, to study the variability of the M dwarf stars in the Pan-STARRS Medium-Deep Field. I will be continuing this project to completion after the semester ends, through this summer. The next step, obviously, is to run the program on all 2,147 catalog images in the Medium-Deep fields, to create a full catalog of hundreds of thousands of M dwarfs. From there, we will use the the ability of Source Extractor to detect sources in one image and do photometry in another to track the sources in the catalog over all the images collected, in chronological order. This will produce a light curve in each color band for each M dwarf. It will then be our task to decide how to describe the variability of those light-curves in a quantifiable, tracking both sudden, short term flares and longer-scale variability in brightness. We can sort the sample based on various properties, such as spectral type and location in the sky, to see if any of these factors have an impact on the behavior of its stellar population. Our ultimate goal would be to create a model predicting the frequency, intensity, and duration of stellar brightening as a function of these factors, in order to better

understand how the properties of a star affect its magnetic field.

Long-term work would involve using what we have gleaned observationally from this study to model magnetic field creation on M dwarfs or habitability around M dwarfs.

Astrobiologists can attempt to simulate the average variability of a type of M dwarf to see what adverse effects it might have on a planet orbiting in its habitable zone. Helioseismologists can attempt to create models of magnetic field creation and flare production that mimic results seen observationally. This study, in fact, has the potential to serve as the large-statistics observational data pool to not only define the “average” behavior of an M dwarf of varying spectral type, but identify outliers and unusual cases worth studying in greater detail.

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